

REFLECTIVE THINKING AS LEARNING STRATEGY IN IMPROVING COGNITIVE SKILLS OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN

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ABSTRACT

The study focused on determining the effect of using reflective thinking strategy on the cognitive skills of the Grade 9 students in Dr. Panfilo Castro National High School for the school year 2020 – 2021. The experimental method of research was used in the study. The subjects of this study were the one hundred (100) students from Grade Nine classes of Dr. Panfilo Castro National High School which are chosen randomly. The study used several instruments such as researcher made survey questionnaire, pre-test, Lesson Exemplars Employing the Teaching of Reflective Thinking Skills and post-test which were administered to the respondents by the researcher. On the demographic profile of the respondents, It was found out that the age of most respondents belonged to the age bracket of 14-16 years old. While in terms of gender, female dominated the study for having the most frequency. On the availability of sources of educational materials the use of books has the highest frequency considered as respondents most available educational resource at home. And for residential pattern, most of the respondents reside at rural area. It was found out the pre-test scores of the students on reflective thinking strategy with regards to writing, critical and problem solving skills were all in the level of approaching proficient. While the post-test scores of the students as to problem solving showed the highest frequency in the approaching proficient level among the two other cognitive skills critical and writing. There is significant difference between the pre-test and post test scores of the students. The mean pre-test and post-test scores obtained by students exposed to reflective thinking strategy significantly differ in terms of writing, critical thinking and problem solving skill. It can be concluded that after using Reflective Thinking Strategy in the teaching and learning process there has a great effect in improving the cognitive skills of Grade 9 students in Araling Panlipunan. From the initial result to the final result of the tests undertaken by the respondents, there is a clear indication that an increase in the cognitive performance of the students took place. Based on the findings and conclusions made in the study, the following recommendations are given; Students, as the main beneficiary of the study, are recommended to take part in improving their cognitive skill through reflective thinking or thinking about or reflecting on what they do. Likewise, Teachers may use these reflective thinking strategy. These may make teaching and learning more effective for the needs of diverse learners and improve cognitive skills of the students amidst to pandemic. Moreover, School administrators may be in the better position to provide teachers more trainings and seminars on the new teaching strategies that can make teaching and learning process more improved and to respond to the needs of learners in various learning modality. Lastly, Future researchers may conduct other Teaching Strategy leading to the other domains of K to 12 Araling Panlipunan Curriculum in relation to students improvement of cognitive skills.

They may determine improvements of cognitive skills on other level of students as those in the elementary level or senior high school.

Keywords: demographic profile, cognitive skills, reflective thinking strategy, problem solving skills